

Natural and economic determinants in the territorial organization of settlements in the municipality of Prizren

Vloran Cenaj

Faculty of History and Philology, University of Tirana, PhD. Candidate, Albania, Tirana

Received: Feb 23, 2026

Accepted: Mar 20, 2026

Published: Apr 18, 2026

Abstract

This paper aims to analyze the spatial distribution, structure and density of settlements in the municipality of Prizren, taking into account the influence of natural, historical and socio-economic factors on the formation and development of settlements. The analysis is based on a geographical and territorial approach which enables the emergence of relationships between the natural environment and social processes that have influenced the spatial organization of settlements.

The study addresses the typology of settlements, their distribution according to altitude, as well as the main characteristics of the territorial structure that distinguish this geographical area. We will also highlight the analysis of the interaction between natural conditions and socio-economic processes that have played a role in the evolution and transformation of the settlement network in this municipality. The final research data provide an important scientific basis for a deeper understanding of the spatial organization of settlements and for the identification of the main factors that influence their development. Also, the study findings represent an important contribution to the processes of territorial planning and sustainable local development.

Keywords: *settlements, municipality of Prizren, altitude, density of settlements.*

Introduction

The municipality of Prizren includes most of the southern part of the Prizren Basin and parts of Pashtrik in the west, Koritnik in the southwest and Sharr Mountain in the south. The area is attractive because in a relatively small area, different categories of geological and pedological composition, relief, climatic elements, as well as plant cover are combined. Relief is undoubtedly the most important of the natural elements that divide the whole into separate wholes and to which it attributes distinctive elements. From a demographic point of view, the municipality of Prizren is quite interesting, due to its national composition, as well as its historical past. The municipality of Prizren is indeed a very interesting region as it is distinguished by many uniform features, in this municipality there are 76 settlements with a total of 147,246 inhabitants¹. The distribution of settlements is the result of a complex interaction between natural and socio-economic factors. Natural factors such as geographical position, morphological configuration of the relief,

¹ KAS, Population by gender, ethnicity and place of residence 2024, Pristina, July 2025. Page 33.

pedological characteristics of the soil and availability of water resources, create the physical-geographical basis for the establishment and development of settlements. Meanwhile, historical, economic, demographic and socio-cultural factors directly affect the functional organization, spatial structure, density and typology of settlements, reflecting the processes of social and economic development in a given geographical area. In the municipality of Prizren, the structure of settlements is characterized by a diverse spatial distribution, where in addition to the developed urban center, a considerable number of rural settlements are also present. These settlements are located mainly in the lowland areas of the Dukagjini Plain, along the Lumbardh River valley, as well as on the slopes of the surrounding hilly-mountainous areas. The geographical position and diverse relief directly affect the way of life and the local economic structure, where in addition to urban and commercial activities in the city of Prizren, agricultural and livestock activities continue to be important in rural areas. This paper analyzes the structure and distribution of settlements in the municipality of Prizren, assessing the impact of geographical and social factors on their formation and development. The paper aims to provide a detailed overview of the characteristics of this area, taking into account the impact of the relief, natural resources, infrastructure, economic connections and social relations that have influenced the organization of the settlement space. The analysis aims to highlight the patterns of settlement distribution, demographic characteristics and the impact of environmental and cultural factors on the urban and rural development of the municipality.

Literature Review

Research on the structure and distribution of settlements in the Municipality of Prizren is based on various geographical, statistical and institutional literature and sources. In terms of geography, the works of Dr. Esat Haskuka and Dr. Riza I Çavolli provide a broad overview of the space of this municipality, analyzing the relief, physical features and historical developments that have influenced the formation and typology of settlements. From a statistical perspective, the Population Census data (REKOS, 2011) and information from the Kosovo Agency of Statistics (KAS) provide detailed data on the demographic distribution by settlements. Also, topographic maps at a scale of 1: 50,000 are used for morphological analysis and for the accurate placement of settlements on the ground.

In institutional terms, the document "Zonal Map of the Municipality of Prizren 2022-2030" reflects the efforts for sustainable development and infrastructure improvement. This combination of geographical, statistical studies and institutional documents provides a solid basis for the analysis of the distribution of settlements in Prizren, enabling the identification of different typologies and challenges of urban and rural development.

Methodology and Research Scheme

For the implementation of this work, several research methods have been used which enable the analysis and interpretation of data in an accurate and reliable manner for the Municipality of Prizren

Geographic Information Systems GIS has been used as a basic tool for the collection, processing and analysis of spatial data, enabling the study of the distribution of settlements and their characteristics in the field.

Remote Sensing through this method, satellite images and aerial photographs have provided detailed spatial information, which have been used to verify and supplement the data collected in the field.

The comparative method has been used to assess the differences and similarities between different areas and historical periods, offering a broad developmental and comparative perspective.

Geographical Analysis has enabled the study of the spatial distribution and physical characteristics of the region, taking into account natural elements such as relief, climate typology, distribution of water resources and soil types.

Historical Analysis has enabled the examination of previous development and their impact on the current state of the settlements of the municipality, providing a deeper understanding of the development process.

The combined use of these methods has enabled an integrated and multidimensional approach to the study of the settlements of the Municipality of Prizren, providing a solid basis for the analysis and interpretation of the results.

Geographical position. Its borders and extent

The municipality of Prizren is one of the 38 municipalities of Kosovo, with an area of 627 km²². With this area, within the total area of Dukagjini (4326 km²³), it participates with 14.49%, while in that of Kosovo (10906 km²) with 5.74%. According to the 2024 census, 147246 inhabitants ⁴live in this municipality with a population density of 235 inhabitants per square kilometer. It lies in the southwestern part of Kosovo. Its geographical position lies between the northern latitudes 42° 05'00" and 42° 21'12", as well as between the eastern longitudes 20° 37'30" and 20°59'00". The area of this municipality includes the southern, largest part of the Prizren valley and the branches of the Sharr Mountains in the south, Korenik in the southwest and Pashtrik in the west.

Map 1 Geographical position of the municipality of Prizren in Kosovo

General physical and geographical characteristics of the municipality of Prizren

² KAS Population Census Atlas. Settlements and municipalities, geographical and administrative division of Kosovo, December 2013. Page 10.

³ Riza Çavolli, Dukagjin (Metohija) Fizionomska i Nadalno – Funkcionalna Regionalizacija, Priština 1977. Pg. 309.

⁴ KAS, Population, Household and Housing Census in Kosovo 2024, Population by gender, ethnicity and place of residence, Pristina July 2025 p.33

In the relief of this area, three main parts are distinguished: the plain area, the mountain range area and the mountainous area. The distance of 88-122 km from the sea, as well as the Drin i Bardh valley, through which the influence of the Mediterranean climate is felt, is of great importance for the climatic conditions of this area. The territorial length of about 44 km, in an almost parallel direction, creates conditions for climatic differences between the extreme parts of this municipality. Local climatic changes determined by the relief are also of considerable importance. In general, this municipality has a mild continental climate with a Mediterranean-type influence. However, the western parts are wetter than the eastern ones. The maritime influence is also noticeable in the fact that autumn is warmer than spring, with the maximum amount of precipitation falling in autumn. In relation to the petrographic structure and the unevenness of the amount of water in the watercourses, as well as the relative richness of atmospheric precipitation, the territory of the Prizren municipality is rich in springs and rivers. However, these also pose serious problems for this region. The high water level during spring and autumn is associated with flooding, while the low water level during summer requires artificial irrigation. For this reason, the need for land improvement (reclamation) arose early. While the lowlands are known for their problems of flooding and irrigation, the areas at the foot of the mountain ranges and especially the mountain peaks are distinguished by soil erosion. The pedological cover of this area is heterogeneous and consists of a large number of soils formed in the place of their creation, while other soils are brought by rivers. They are formed partly from lake sediments, partly from fluvioglacial materials and partly from new materials brought by flowing waters. The vegetation of this territory is a reflection of many elements and factors. Of the natural elements, the most important are the climate and the pedological base. However, the vegetation in its current state has also been influenced by human factors. The traditional form of economy, with the main branches of unprofitable agriculture and small livestock farming, has led to the damage of the plant cover and, in connection with this, erosion in the areas at the foot of the mountains and on the mountain ridges has intensified.

This municipality borders Albania to the west, Dragash to the south, Macedonia to the southeast, Štrpce to the east, Suhareka to the northeast, Rahovec to the north, Mamusha to the northeast and Gjakova to the northwest. The territory of the Prizren municipality is characterized by different altitudes above sea level. The lowest point of the Prizren municipality is located in the valley of the Drini i Bardhë river, on the border with Albania and reaches a height of 270 m above sea level, while the highest point is located southeast of Prizren, on the border with North Macedonia in the Sharr-Bistër Mountains (Peskovi) at 2,651 m.

Population movements in the municipality of Prizren

During the 30-year period (from 1981 to 2011), no population census was conducted in Kosovo, and also during the 13-year period (from 2011 to 2024), the population census in Kosovo, which was scheduled to take place in 2021, was not conducted for several main reasons related to political, organizational challenges, and the COVID-19 pandemic. In the 1991 census, the population of Kosovo did not participate in this census conducted at that time by the Serbian government. During this period of time, in the absence of population data, various estimates from both local and international institutions and organizations were used.

The population census conducted in 2011 and 2024 provides more accurate and up-to-date data on population, households, and housing. Therefore, in presenting data on the population of the Municipality of Prizren, we will rely on the data of these censuses, despite the fact that the 2011 and 2024 censuses have some shortcomings in terms of professional, technical aspects and also related to political circumstances.

According to the results of the 2024 census, the Municipality of Prizren has a total of 147,246 inhabitants.⁵

Chart 1: Population according to censuses 1948 – 2024

Based on the analyses of the basic and ranged population growth index in the Municipality of Prizren, we can observe a clear change in demographic development.

Table 1. Population size according to basic and range index⁶

Years	Population No.	Basic index	String Index
Recording 1948	53261	100	
Recording 1953	58251	109.37	109.37
Recording 1961	68453	128.52	117.51
Recording 1971	95676	179.64	139.77
Recording 1981	131774	246.29	137.10
Recording 1991	175426	329.37	133.74
Recording 2011	177781	333.79	101.34
Recording 2024	147246	276.46	82.82

⁵ KAS, Population by gender, ethnicity and place of residence 2024, July 2025, p. 33

⁶ Statistical Office of Kosovo, Population, Households by Place of Residence and Territorial Organization of Kosovo until 2008, Pristina, September 2008, pp. 80-82. KAS, Population, Households and Housing Census in Kosovo 2011, Population by Gender, Ethnicity and Place of Residence, Pristina April 2013, pp. 45-46. KAS, Population, Households and Housing Census in Kosovo 2024, Demographic Data by Municipality, July 2025, Pristina, pp. 15-16.

From 1948 to 2011, the population of the Municipality of Prizren has increased by about 124,520 inhabitants, which is considered a rapid increase, the basic index increases from 100 to 329, which means a tripling of the population within 43 years, the serial index shows a strong increase in each census (over 100), especially in 1971 where the serial index reaches 139.77 and 1981 reaches 137.10. The period from 1991 to 2011 is considered as stagnation, where the population increases very little from 175,426 inhabitants to 177,781 inhabitants, the serial index falls to 101.34, which shows almost zero growth. This is related to the period of massive emigration of Albanians towards Western Europe as a result of the difficult political and economic circumstances that the population of Kosovo went through.

While for the period 1948 to 2024 there has been an increase of about 93985, that is, less by 30535 inhabitants, as a result of the fact that the population of the municipality of Prizren for the period from 2011 to 2024 has suffered a decrease by -30535 inhabitants, this is an example of the demographic transition from a society with a high birth rate to a society with high emigration and lower birth rate. In some time periods, a smaller population increase has been recorded and in others a higher increase. What stands out from the table and graph is the period between the 2011 census and the 2024 census, where the data show a decrease in the number of the population within a 13-year period. This phenomenon is explained by the fact that this census did not include residents who are in different countries of Europe and the World.

Average density of settlements and spatial distance

Of particular importance in this case would be the analysis of the spatial density of settlements and their average distance, which is determined based on quantitative mathematical methods. Thus, the average density is obtained by dividing the number of settlements and the area of a certain area, where 100 km is taken for an area.⁷

For this purpose, the formula is used $T = \frac{n \cdot 100}{S}$ which shows⁸

n= the number of settlements

S= siperfaqen e territorit not km²

$$T = \frac{n \cdot 100}{S} = \frac{76 \cdot 100}{627 \text{ km}^2} = \frac{7600}{627 \text{ km}^2} = 12.12 \text{ vendbanime / km}^2$$

⁷ Ibrahim Ramadani Rural Development, organization and spatial regulation of settlements in the Kosovo region, Dukagjini, Peja, 2004, p. 123.

⁸ M. Radovanovič, S. Nikolič, Dispersion as a quantitative parameter of spatial distribution and methods for the study of rural settlements, Zbornik radova, Gl.sv.xx.Belgrade, 1973, f.104.

Dendesia e settlements before 12.12 settlements not 100 km² shows the average distribution of these settlements in the commune. Vendbanimet nuk jane shume te ralla, por as shume te dendura. Ato jane te shperndara ne menyre compatible te nydal ne hapësir, duke lene hapësira te hydtrashme per toke bujqesore, natyr dhe aktivitete te tyra ekonomiki. What type and settlements are shown are the natural and economic conditions that lead to the balance of rural and urban development. Banoret kane mundesi te zhvillojn bujqesin, blegtorin dhe activities te tyra, ndersa abodezhdet langin te connected mes tyre perms rüvve dhe infrastructures.

The density of the settlement network is also expressed through the spatial distance of settlements and logarithms

using the formula $D = \sqrt{\frac{s}{n}}$, Therefore, based on this, the average distance between settlements in the municipality of

Prizren is: 2.87 km².

$$D = \sqrt{\frac{s}{n}} = \sqrt{\frac{627 \text{ km}^2}{76}} = \sqrt{8.25} = 2.87 \text{ km}$$

s= surface area in km²

n = number of settlements⁹

Typology of settlements according to geographical position

The municipality of Prizren is located in the southwestern part of Kosovo and is known for its three parts of relief. The territory of the municipality includes mountainous areas, lowlands and plains, which create a natural diversity with special geographical, climatic and economic characteristics. This mosaic makes Prizren one of the richest municipalities in terms of landscape and natural potential.

It is known that the influence of relief on the creation of settlements is very large, the most suitable conditions for the construction of settlements are offered in the plain areas, this is why most of the territory of the municipality of Prizren has all the favorable conditions for the construction of rural and urban settlements, the relief also determines the shape of the settlement. During the construction and development of settlements, interventions in agricultural areas should be avoided, in this regard, if possible, unproductive and less productive lands should be used. However, it should be noted that this terrain is also seismically unstable.

The mountainous area constitutes the southern and southeastern part of the municipality and is dominated by the Sharr mountain range. These mountains are among the highest in Kosovo, with altitudes reaching over 2000 meters, while some peaks such as Luboten and Pashtriku are known for their harsh climates and rich biodiversity. The mountainous

⁹ KAS, Population, Household and Housing Census in Kosovo 2011, Population by gender, ethnicity and place of residence, Pristina April 2013, pp. 45-46.

area is characterized by rugged terrain, narrow valleys, numerous water sources and dense forests. It has great potential for mountain tourism, winter sports and an economy based on livestock.

The entire complex of the mountainous area, in addition to its hypsographic differentiation, is characterized by its geological composition, low temperatures and pronounced humidity. Accordingly, the ecological conditions are more suitable for mountain agriculture. Rye, barley and oats dominate the main cereal crops. In addition, the mountainous area is also important for the use of forests and pastures for livestock. Given the pronounced slope, the mountainous area is very important for the use of the hydropower potential of the rivers. Many natural phenomena, such as the broken relief, the dense network of rivers, water sources and specific climatic conditions, make this area special from a geographical and ecological point of view. These factors have directly influenced the way the space is used, the distribution of settlements and the development of traditional economic activities, especially livestock farming and the use of natural resources. Between the mountainous areas and the Prizren Basin lies the Rrënzëmali area, which constitutes an intermediate relief of medium altitude. This area has undulating terrain, low hills and often fertile soil that is suitable for agriculture, viticulture and fruit growing. The numerous villages of this area, such as Korisha, Reçan or Randobrava, traditionally use these natural resources. The foothills area is of particular importance for the natural and economic connection between the mountains and the plain. The plain area extends to the northern and northeastern part of the municipality and includes the Prizren Plain. This area is characterized by flat terrain and low altitude, which make it suitable for intensive agriculture and urban development. It is here that the city of Prizren, the historical, cultural and economic center of the municipality, is located. The plain area has a higher population density and a concentration of infrastructure, which has facilitated the development of light industry and services. In general, the relief of the Municipality of Prizren represents a natural harmony between high mountains, gentle hills and wide plains. This diversity not only gives the municipality a diverse landscape, but also directly affects its economic, cultural and tourist life. Therefore, the relief of the Municipality of Prizren can be considered a key factor in the multifaceted development of this region and an important natural asset that should be carefully preserved and used. The settlements of the municipality of Prizren are distributed in the lowland area at an altitude of 250 to 500 meters above sea level, in the sub-mountainous area between 500 and 1000 meters above sea level and in the mountainous area above 1000 meters above sea level. The settlements that are distributed in the lowland area at an altitude of 250 to 500 meters above sea level are 43 settlements: 1. Atmaxhë, 2. Caparc, 3. Dedaj, 4. Dobrushtë (Mirez), 5. Dushanovë, 6. Grazhdanikë, 7. Gjonaj, 8. Hoc e Qytetit, 9. Kabash i Hasit, 10. Kobaj, 11. Kojushë, 12. Korishë, 13. Krajk, 14. Krushë e Vogël, 15. Kushnin, 16. Landovicë, 17. Lubizhdë, 18. Lubizhd e Hasit (Lugishta), 19. Lukinaj, 20. Lutogllava (Legend), 21. Malesi e Re, 22. Medvec (Iiliras), 23. Muradem, 24. Nashec, 25. Novak, 26. Pertovë, 27. Piranë, 28. Poslishtë (Gurrë), 29. Randobravë (Qendresa), 30. Romajë, 31. Serbic

Table no. 2. Number and percentage of settlements according to hypsometric levels within the area of the municipality of Prizren

Hypsometric floors	Number of settlements	%
< 500	43	56.57%
501 deri 1000	23	30.26%
1001 deri 1500	10	13.15%
totali	76	100%

The impact of altitude on the socio-economic development of settlements in the municipality of Prizren

One of the main natural factors that affects the spatial organization and socio-economic development of settlements in the municipality of Prizren is the altitude of the settlements. Based on the processed data for the settlements of this municipality, it results that the average altitude of the settlements is about 575 meters above sea level. This value shows that the territory of the municipality is characterized by a diverse relief, where plain, hilly and mountainous areas are combined, creating different natural and socio-economic conditions for the development of settlements. From the analysis of the data, we note that the settlements with the lowest altitude lie about 312 meters above sea level, as in the case of Kruše e Vogel, Nashec and Zojzi, which are located in the plain part of the municipal territory. On the other hand, the settlement with the highest altitude is Kabashi, which lies at about 1260 meters above sea level and belongs to the mountainous area of the Sharr Mountains. The difference between these two extreme values reaches about 948 meters, which testifies to a considerable hypsometric amplitude and to a pronounced morphological diversity within the territory of the municipality of Prizren.

The distribution of settlements according to hypsometric levels shows that 43 settlements are located at an altitude below 500 meters, 23 settlements in the interval 501-1000 meters, while 10 settlements lie at an altitude above 1000 meters above sea level. This hypsometric configuration shows that most settlements are concentrated in plain and hilly areas, which offer more favorable conditions for the development of agriculture, the construction of infrastructure and the concentration of the population.

From a socio-economic point of view, altitude directly affects the economic structure of settlements. In areas with lower altitudes, intensive agricultural activities dominate and settlements develop more rapidly, thanks to more fertile soils and more favorable climatic conditions. Meanwhile, in areas with higher altitudes, especially in areas related to the mountainous relief of the Sharr Mountains, traditional activities such as livestock farming, pasture exploitation and, in recent years, the development of mountain tourism are more present.

In this context, altitude represents an important component in the geographical analysis of the territory of the Municipality of Prizren, as it affects not only the physical characteristics of the environment, but also the demographic, economic and social organization of settlements. Consequently, the study of the hypsometric distribution of settlements offers an important basis for spatial planning and sustainable development of the municipal territory.

Table no. 2. Average altitude of settlements within the municipality of Prizren¹⁰

No.	Residence	Altitude (m)	No.	Residence	Altitude (m)
1	Atmaxhë	368	39	Manastiricë	1019
2	Billushë	535	40	Mazrek	500
3	Caparc	375	41	Medvec	314
4	Dedaj	393	42	Milaj	700
5	Dobrushtë	354	43	Muradem	325
6	Dojnicë	990	44	Mushnikovë	908
7	Drajçiq	1047	45	Nashec	312
8	Dushanovë	382	46	Nebregoshtë	898
9	Gërçar	699	47	Novak	340
10	Gornjasellë	1126	48	Novosellë	1030
11	Gorozhup	585	49	Petrovë	379
12	Grazhdanik	350	50	Piranë	320
13	Gjonaj	415	51	Pllanejë	660
14	Hoçë e Qytetit	404	52	Pllanjan	865
15	Jabllanicë ¹	980	53	Poslishtë	354
16	Jeshkovë	545	54	Pouskë ²	700
17	Kabash	1260	55	Prizren	400
18	Kabash i Hasit	349	56	Randobravë	370
19	Karashëngjergj	623	57	Reçan	607
20	Kobajë	354	58	Romajë	320
21	Kojushë	482	59	Sërbicë e Epërme	334
22	Korishë	447	60	Sërbicë e Poshtme	323
23	Krajk	345	61	Skorobishtë	975
24	Krushë e Vogël	312	62	Smaç	336
25	Kushnin	395	63	Sredskë	724
26	Kushtendil	1030	64	Struzhë	1169
27	Landovicë	334	65	Shkozë	419
28	Leskovec	850	66	Shpenadi	382
29	Lez	1000	67	Trepetnicë	353
30	Lubinjë e Epërme	1062	68	Tupec	337
31	Lubinjë e Poshtme	877	69	Velezhë	354
32	Lubiqevë	610	70	Vërbiçan	1000
33	Lubizhdë	451	71	Vërmicë	335
34	Lubizhdë e Hasit	400	72	Vlashnjë	326
35	Lukinaj	313	73	Zojz	312
36	Lutogllavë	406	74	Zym	586
37	Llokvicë	872	75	Zhivinjan	750
38	Malësi e Re	400	76	Zhur	436

¹⁰ Data on the altitude of settlements were obtained from the topographic map of the Military Geographic Institute 1: 100,000 - Prizren no. 680. The content of the map is based on the terrain conditions from 1962-1965.

Conclusion

According to the analysis, we note that the territory of the municipality of Prizren is characterized by a diverse relief, where settlements lie at altitudes ranging from 312 meters to 1260 meters above sea level. The average altitude of settlements is about 572 meters, reflecting a dominance of hilly and partly mountainous areas, while the city of Prizren is located about 400 meters above sea level, as an urban and socio-economic center. The distribution according to hypsometric levels shows that the majority of settlements (43 out of 76) are located at altitudes below 500 meters, 23 settlements are located in the interval 501-1000 meters and 10 settlements lie above 1000 meters. This distribution structure reflects the influence of the relief on the development of economic activities, where the lower areas benefit from more favorable climatic conditions and fertile soil, while the mountainous areas offer conditions for the development of traditional activities such as livestock farming, mountain tourism and beekeeping. The large variation in altitude has a direct impact on the demographic structure, spatial organization and socio-economic development of these settlements. High settlements are characterized by lower population density, more difficult access to infrastructure and public services, but at the same time offer great potential for sustainable economic development through the use of natural resources and tourism. In this context, altitude is a key factor that must be taken into account in spatial planning, the drafting of development policies and the allocation of infrastructure investments. An integrated approach, based on the hypsometric distribution and climatic characteristics of settlements, can contribute to the sustainable development of the territory of the municipality of Prizren and to the increase of the well-being of its communities.

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